

WAYS TO ACCELERATE BUSINESS ACTIVITY IN VILLAGES

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ABSTRACT

It should be noted that conditions for the deagrarianization of the rural economy, the wide spread of new forms of farming and the development of alternative types of activities in the countryside have been ensured. quality of life of rural residents. One of the factors that have a significant impact on the development of entrepreneurship in the countryside is the personal potential of entrepreneurs, which is distinguished by significant regional differences.

INTRODUCTION.

Entrepreneurship in the village is carried out in a certain environment, which is a set of external and internal conditions for the implementation of entrepreneurial activities (Figure 1.1.1). At the same time, such conditions may differ significantly depending on regional and network characteristics.

Figure 1.1.1. Features of the business environment in rural areas¹.

Rural entrepreneurship is closely connected with the external environment and has a direct impact on it. The latter is an activator of formation of entrepreneurial activities and increasing the level of entrepreneurial activity. In particular, the environment affects the formation of the entrepreneurial environment, labor potential, and quality of life in the village.

In turn, entrepreneurship determines the economic, social and environmental conditions of rural development. Against the background of the above, it can be said that the need to create an appropriate organizational and economic platform for the development of entrepreneurship in the village is related to the uniqueness of the network and its implementation, as well as the changing internal working conditions. and the external environment.

One of the mandatory components of the definition of entrepreneurial activity is its psychological aspect, because the results of a number of studies show that the central link on which the success of entrepreneurial activity depends is the personality of the entrepreneur, his direction, the individual typological characteristics of this person, his mental processes, and his formation and integration with the self-management system.

Entrepreneurs value their independence and self-confidence, opportunities for earning and self-fulfillment, which is related to information related to the evaluation of the content and motivations of entrepreneurs' entrepreneurial activity. At the next stage of the research, it is desirable to distinguish and systematize the signs of entrepreneurship in rural areas,

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which will allow to identify it as a socio-economic phenomenon spreading in various areas of the national economy from the established list of entrepreneurship signs.

Figure 1.1.2. Signs of entrepreneurship in rural areas².

So, the uniqueness, independence, initiative, purposefulness, availability of entrepreneurial ability, responsibility, flexibility, risk-taking, independence, innovation, self-organization, self-interest, competence, mobility of the field of entrepreneurship in the village. When determining the specific features of entrepreneurial activity in rural areas, it should be emphasized that one of the distinctive features of its successful operation in modern conditions is a balanced combination of marketing management principles with classical features of entrepreneurial activity. Therefore, it is appropriate to include the marketing direction of business activity in the list of established characteristics (Figure 1.1.2).

Marketing is an important argument in favor of the activation of entrepreneurship as a set of ideology and means of studying and influencing the market. In the conditions of the complexity of the rural economy, whose characteristic features are the expansion of the information and communication space, the business sector requires constant monitoring of the market in order to quickly respond to the changes taking place, to correct directions and forms. economic activity.

At the same time, an important condition for the long-term development of enterprises is their adaptation to changes in the market environment and the speed of reaction. Accordingly, marketing management is one of the foundations of business activity in modern conditions. Given that rural development reserves are not only additional investments, but

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also in the formation of their competitive status, rural areas also need professional marketing, such as goods or services.

Figure 1.1.3. A set of criteria for determining entrepreneurship in rural areas³.

This is due to the fact that the application of marketing technologies significantly expands the possibilities of effective use of regional assets as a place of business and life activity of the rural population. Adequate marketing support for the development of rural areas serves to attract the local population to create the necessary conditions and measures for the activation of small and medium-sized businesses, self-sufficiency, and ensuring the financial capabilities of villages. It is important to determine the principles and criteria for business entities operating in rural areas (Figure 1.1.3).

Therefore, consider independence, institutionalization, innovation, socialization, flexibility as the main principles of rural entrepreneurship development; Placement of production facilities in the village, involvement of the villagers to perform work, development of various types of activities, social and environmental responsibility, implementation of creative ideas and ideas of entrepreneurs are criteria.

The entrepreneurial ability of an entrepreneur is not limited to entrepreneurial activity and it is necessarily complemented by the entrepreneur's knowledge, experience, knowledge and skills. In addition, self-organization (the ability to carry out coherent, logically connected and purposeful actions) appears to be a prerequisite for the implementation of the main entrepreneurial function.

At the same time, it is worth noting that entrepreneurial activity in the village is formed under the influence of a set of informal institutions such as experience, traditions, and business culture specific to the respective rural area. Thus, in a generalized form, entrepreneurship in the village is the activity of independent, self-initiated, self-initiated

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business entities in certain environmental conditions for the purpose of obtaining economic, social, ecological benefits and self-realization.

Taking into account the specified characteristics, characteristics of the development environment, implementation criteria and principles, as well as summarizing the opinions of scholars on the interpretation of entrepreneurship in rural areas, it is proposed to consider it from the point of view of the implementation of the main principles. The multifunctionality of the rural economy, which not only takes into account the set of organizational and economic factors of ensuring the balanced growth of the village, but also provides opportunities for entrepreneurs to capitalize on their business ideas and realize their potential in order to achieve commercial success.

Taking into account the established rules and taking into account the specific features and problems of the current stage of strengthening the European integration processes, it is appropriate to study the organizational-economic platform as the main factor for the development of entrepreneurship in the countryside. formation of business space.

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